

Trends in Intellectual Property Research

Improving Indicators in Intellectual Property Rights Enforcement in Pakistan: A Study of Impact of Integrated IP Management Model

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Abstract: This study highlights the present situation of enforcement of Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) and its improvement as an impact of implementation of integrated IP management system in Pakistan. The key initiatives taken by the national government and the organization to achieve the target have been discussed in this study. The major steps include centralized IP administration, new IP legislation, up-gradation of IP Laws, introduction of special IP courts as IP tribunal, capacity building of IP personnel, digitization & automation, cooperation & interaction between law and enforcement agencies & departments, accession to international treaties and IP awareness across the country etc. The aforesaid actions made positive image of the country in IPRs situation by improvement in global IPR ranking index.

Keywords: IPO Pakistan; IP Enforcement; IP Tribunal; Enforcement Committee; Pakistan IP Ranking

1. Introduction

Before 2005, the administration of Intellectual Property (IP) laws fragmented in Pakistan with different Ministries like the Patent & Design office, the Copyright Office and the Trade mark Registry were under the Federal Ministry of Industries & Production, Federal Ministry of Education and Federal Ministry of Commerce, respectively. The IPRs administration is one of the federal subjects and is on the Forth Schedule of Federal Legislative List (FLL. clause 25)¹ of the Pakistan. The situation of enforcement of IP rights in the country was not satisfactory.

On April 8, 2005, a central autonomous body Intellectual Property Organization of Pakistan (IPO-Pakistan) was established under an Ordinance of 2005 (Ordinance No. V of 2005)², for integrated and efficient intellectual property management in the country under the administrative control of the Cabinet Division, Federal Government of Pakistan which was later transferred to Commerce Division, Ministry of Commerce (Rule of Business 1973, p.35)³ on July 25, 2016. However, at present, IPO Pakistan is working under Intellectual Property Organization of Pakistan Act, 2012 (IPO Act 2012)⁴. The Patents Ordinance, 2000; the Registered Design Ordinance, 2000; the Copyright Ordinance 1962; the Registered Layout-Designs of Integrated Circuits Ordinance, 2000 and the Trade Marks Ordinance, 2001, were made as schedule law of IPO Act, 2012⁴. Accordingly, the concerned offices were made under the direct supervision of IPO Pakistan. In this Act of 2012⁴, the organization was made responsible for strengthening and enforcement of IPRs the

¹ Pakistan Federal Legislative List. <https://www.pakistani.org/pakistan/constitution/schedules/schedule4.html> (Accessed 15 December 2023).

² The Pakistan Intellectual Property Rights Organization Ordinance, 2005 (Ordinance No. V of 2005). Senate https://www.cpdipakistan.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/04/Parliamentary_Alert_II_Performance_of_the_Senate_November_2005.pdf.

³ Pakistan Rules of Business 1973 (revised 2018). <https://moitt.gov.pk/SitelImage/Misc/files/%5BROB%20amended%20upto%204th%20April%2C%202018.pdf>.

⁴ Intellectual Property Organization of Pakistan Act, 2012. <https://ipo.gov.pk/system/files/IPO-Act-2012.pdf>.

actions in the country. This approach of integrated set up /model impacted the conventional IP system of Pakistan and resulted into positive outcomes.

2. Pakistan as Member of International Treaties on IP

Pakistan is member of various international treaties on IP and under these international obligations, Pakistan is supposed to standardize its IPRs implementation polices and effective IP enforcements strategies in the country. Pakistan has acceded the Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works on June 4, 1948⁵; World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) Convention on October 6, 1976⁵; Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS), January 1, 1995⁶; Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property, on April 22, 2004⁵; Madrid Protocol Relating to the Madrid Agreement Concerning the International Registration of Marks on February 24, 2021⁵ and Marrakesh Treaty on accessibility of Copyright work for Visually Impaired Persons (VIP) on December 12, 2023⁷. IPO Pakistan held a number of stakeholder consultative sessions on the subject of accession to Patent Cooperation Treaty (PCT) across the country. The consultative process has been completed now after a final Inter-Ministerial Meeting on the subject proposal of accession to this international treaty. This indicates that the country is in process of accession to PCT.

A responsible country, Pakistan is under obligations of aforesaid treaties to provide favorable environment of recognition of the ownership rights of intellectual creators for residents as well as non-residents. Article 2 and 3 of the Paris Convention stipulates that each Contracting Nation must treat all nationals from the Convention's member states as equal when granting intellectual property protection. National treatment means no discrimination among the applicants of multiple origin in the protection of IP rights and enforcements of registered rights. Further, Article 27 of the TRIPS Agreement⁶ enables patent protection for inventions of all fields of technologies without discrimination subject to fulfillment of patentability requirements. So, we can conclude, a due consideration is to be given to all types of intellectual creativity irrespective of type of intellectual property, origin or residency of the applicant or the creator or the inventor whatever case may be. The seriousness and the implementation status of the international treaties on IP sets the ranking of IPRs situation in the country which ultimately leads to economic feasibility of foreign investment in the country.

3. Ranking of Pakistan in Global IPR Spectrum

An early harvest was observed as an improvement of IPRs enforcement situation in the country, as a fruit of introduction integrated IP management in Pakistan after 2005. Reportedly, 13.4 million of pirated CDs and 227, 420 pirated Books were recovered by Federal Investigation Agency (FIA)⁸, during the raids across the country. The figures recent few years also indicates improvements in the enforce due to effective policy measures taken by the concerned departments. This assessment is based on the international agencies which maintain record of IPRs situation based on multiple factors.

3.1. Global Innovation Index (GII)

⁵ <https://www.wipo.int/wipolex/en/treaties/ShowResults?code=PK>

⁶ https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/countries_e/pakistan_e.htm

⁷ <https://president.gov.pk/news/pakistan-joins-marrakesh-treaty-to-facilitate-access-of-visually-impaired-persons-to-published-work-2#:~:text=to%20published%20work-,Pakistan%20joins%20Marrakesh%20Treaty%20to%20facilitate%20access%20of%20visually%20impaired,work%20for%20visually%20impaired%20persons.>

⁸ <https://fia.gov.pk/ipr#>

The Global Innovation Index (GII) ranks world economies according to their innovation capabilities. GI ranking is indexed based on almost 80 indicators, grouped into innovation inputs and outputs, the GI aims to capture the multi-dimensional facets of innovation. The GI 2023 report shows statistical confidence interval of the ranking of Pakistan is between ranks 84 and 100. Pakistan ranks 5th among the 10 economies in Central and Southern Asia and ranks 12th among the 37 lower-middle-income group economies. The table 1 indicates GI rankings of Pakistan over the past four years.⁹

Table 1. Global Innovation Index ranking of Pakistan.

Year	GII Position	Innovation Inputs	Innovation Outputs
2020	107 th	118 th	88 th
2021	99 th	117 th	77 th
2022	87 th	111 th	69 th
2023	88 th	113 th	68 th

This year-by-year refined ranking of IPRS situation of Pakistan is widely acknowledged by national and foreign forums. The media reports like Arab News published an article on Pakistan's GI ranking 99th in year 2021. Asia IP Law also reported Pakistan ranking progress by an article "Pakistan doing very well innovation wise, ranks 87th on Global Innovation Index 2022" by Hasan Irfan Khan published on October 25, 2022 (Asia IP Law, 2022). In this article Khan said "In my opinion, the development of a positive performance innovation wise will tell the policymakers that intellectual property laws need to be improved and implemented effectively as they are needed to protect the innovative products developed by Pakistani startups, few of which are already sending signs of being unicorns out of Pakistan,".

The improvement in Pakistan ranking in GI Report 2023 was also reported by an article of Amin Ahmad published in DAWN News on October 8, 2023 (Ahmad, 2023) with title "Pakistan shines on global innovation benchmark". Where it was reported that Pakistan ranks 88th among the 132 economies featured in the GI. Relative to GDP, Pakistan is performing above expectations for its level of development, the index report said.

3.2. International Property Rights Index (IPRI)

The International Property Rights Index (IPRI) is the flagship publication of Property Rights Alliance. The IPRI is world index which covers 125 countries and score underlie the strength of property rights regime including physical property and intellectual property rights. The IPRI 2023 indicates that Pakistan's overall score has increased by 0.01 to 3.824 placing it 17th in the Asia and Oceania region and 104th in the world as shown in table 2 and 3.¹⁰

Table 2. Overall IPRI score of Pakistan.

Year	Overall Score	Global score	Regional score	Increase / Decrease
2020	4.142	116	18	0.267
2021	4.211	111	18	0.069
2022	3.814	108	18	-0.397
2023	3.824	104	17	0.010

⁹ Global Innovation Index 2023.

https://www.wipo.int/global_innovation_index/en/2023/#:~:text=For%20the%2013th%20year,Global%20Innovation%20Index%202023%20rankings.

¹⁰ International Property Rights Index 2023. <https://www.internationalpropertyrightsindex.org/>

3.3. GIPC International IP Index

International IP Index is administered by Global Innovation Policy Center (GIPC) United States Chamber of Commerce. GIPC IP Index benchmarks the IP framework in 55 global economies including Pakistan based on 50 unique indicators. This IP Index reflects effectiveness of IP standards for the economies by strengthening the ecosystem for innovation and creativity.

Table 3. GIPC IP Index Score of Pakistan.

Year	Overall indication	Global score	Regional score	Increase / Decrease
2020 ¹¹	51/53	26.50%	-	-0.17%
2021 ¹²	52/53	26.43%	15	-0.07%
2022 ¹³	53/55	27.43%	15	+1%
2023 ¹⁴	52/55	27.42%	15	-0.01%

According to GIPC IP index report 2023, Pakistan's overall score has decreased during the year 2022 to 2023 i.e. 27.43% to 27.42%. This reflects a score decrease due to IPRs enforcement of physical property items as reflected by indicator 32 of GIPC IP Index. The other encouraging areas of Pakistan mentioned in the IP Index 2023 include Pakistan's accession to Madrid Protocol, an international treaty on trademark; basic IP laws and legal framework in place; introduction of specialized IP courts and capacity building; greater efforts at public education, modernization of IP laws, and enhancing coordination among enforcement agencies. One of the reasons of low ranking in the IP index is, Pakistan is not a member of Patent Cooperation Treaty (PCT) which has an impact in the regional and international score card of this ranking.

3.4. USTR Special Report 301

The Office of the United States Trade Representative (USTR) prepares a Special 301 Report on an annual basis that identifies trade barriers to United States companies and products due to the intellectual property laws including patents, designs, copyrights and trademarks, in other countries. The categorization of the countries in the 301 USTR is based on the implementation situation of Intellectual Property protection and enforcement in a country specially U.S. trading partners. As reported by USTR released 2023 Special 301 Report on Intellectual Property Protection and Enforcement¹⁵, Pakistan is placed among twenty-two (22) trading partners (countries) on the U.S. Watch List which is a better position than other seven countries which are on the U.S. Priority Watch List including Argentina, Chile, China, India, Indonesia, Russia, and Venezuela, with respect to trade with United States.

3.5. Index of the Property Rights of Heritage Foundation

Pakistan and China gradually improved their poor IPR ranking on the International Property Rights Index of the Heritage Foundation. Sayed Zubair Shah discussed year by year improvements from 2011 to 2022 in Table 1 (Shah, 2023). There has been a tremendous amount of progress in both nations in IPR ranking.

¹¹ GIPC IP Index 2020. https://www.uschamber.com/assets/documents/023881_gipc_ip_index_2020_fullreport_final.pdf

¹² GIPC IP Index 2021. https://www.theglobalipcenter.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/GIPC_IPIndex2021_FullReport_v3.pdf

¹³ GIPC IP Index 2022. <https://www.uschamber.com/intellectual-property/2022-international-ip-index>

¹⁴ GIPC IP Index 2023. <https://www.uschamber.com/intellectual-property/2023-international-ip-index>

¹⁵ USTR Releases 2023 Special 301 Report on Intellectual Property Protection and Enforcement. <https://ustr.gov/issue-areas/intellectual-property/special-301>

However, the economic development, judicial system and political environment of Pakistan, slow down its progress in comparison to China.

3.6. IPRs and Economy

The situation of IP rights in a country is highly critical for competitiveness, growth and sustainability of a country economy. Accordingly, the filing of IP i.e. patents, designs, trademarks, copyrights, Geographical indications, layout designs of topography and are direct measure of R&D level and standard of a country. For example, Patent is mature form of innovative technological development of applied nature as an outcome of R&D. Trademark registration is a harvesting of repute of a quality of a brand or company earned from years of business by maintaining the quality. It is a proven fact, that the developed nations economies are beneficiaries of fruits of their IP rights while developing countries are still lagging behind due to lack of IP which are ultimate result of Research and Development. Pakistan's economy is mainly considered as agriculture-based production. However, this is not true, services sector has a significant share in its economy. For the sustainable economic growth, Pakistan must shift on hi-tech research & development, and knowledge-based economy through innovation and creativity. IP is a powerful driver of innovation and creativity for wealth creation.

Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) has become significant for two countries, due to the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC), a significant component of China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), and IPRs are employed by businesses of all sizes throughout the economies of both nations (Tahir *et al.*, 2022). As the firms of two countries will operate together in a geographical area, so IP protection and enforcement will be vital for business in the same sector. The efforts which caused this improvement of global IP ranking in the country were explored and analyzed. The following factors positively impacted the ranking:

4. IP Legislation in Pakistan

One of the supporting factors to improve the IPRs state in the country, was introduction of new effective IP polices and strategies which required to be covered by the legal backing. The target was achieved by upgradation and promulgation of new IP legislation.

4.1. IPO Pakistan Act, 2012

A new organization Intellectual Property Organization of Pakistan was established for integrated IP management under IPO Act, 2012⁴. The IP offices including Patent and Design Office, Copyright office and trademark Registry were made. This new organization was empowered under Section 13 to inquire, investigate, advise and refer IP violation cases to Law and Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) of Federal and Provincial Governments. Accordingly, under section 37 of IPO-Act, 2012⁴, all concerned law enforcement agencies and authorities in the Federation and the Provinces made under an obligation to provide and render full and complete assistance to the Organization may deem fit and proper to demand or require for carrying out the purposes of this Act.

Similarly, special Intellectual Property Tribunal (IPT) were established under Section 16 of the IPO Act, 2012⁴ for the speedy trial of IP infringement cases instead of Distract Court. This made possible the effective IP enforcement and positive outcome.

4.2. National Intellectual Property Laws

The existing IP laws of the Pakistan provide sufficient remedies including criminal as well as civil, against the violation of registered intellectual property rights under the respective IP law. Table 4 shows a summary of offences and remedies under the concerned law:

Table 4. Remedies against violation of IPRs in Pakistan.

IP Law	Status	Remedies
The Patents Ordinance, 2000	Offence: Infringement Non-Cognizable Offence (Section 60 to 67)	Civil Remedy: Damages and compensation of estimated loss
The Registered Designs Ordinance, 2000	Offence: Infringement Non-Cognizable Offence (Section 8)	Civil Remedy: Damages and compensation of estimated loss
The Copyrights Ordinance, 1962	Offence: Piracy Cognizable and Non-bailable Offence (Section 66 -74)	Maximum imprisonment up to 3 years. Fine up to one-hundred thousand rupees. Double Fine on repetition of offence. Civil Remedy: Damages and compensation of estimated loss
The Trade Mark Ordinance, 2001	Offence: Counterfeiting Non-Cognizable Offence (Section 99 to 107)	Maximum imprisonment up to 2 years. Minimum fine Rs. 50,000 Civil Remedy: Damages and compensation of estimated loss

4.3. The Pakistan Penal Code, 1860

In addition to existing IP laws, the Sections 478, 479, 480, 481, 482, 483, 485, 486, 487, 488 and 489 of the Pakistan Penal Code, 1860 (PPC, 1860)¹⁶ are included in the schedule of IPO-Act, 2012⁴. These provisions of PPC, 1860 are applicable on violation (Counterfeiting) of registered Trademarks and Merchandize marks. The punishment for representation, making or procession, selling, and or tampering of false trademark goods are declared as offence and made punishable under aforesaid sections of the PPC, 1860.

4.4. The Customs Act, 1969 of Pakistan

The Custom Act, 1969 (IV of 1969)¹⁷ of Pakistan prohibits to brought into the country, the goods with counterfeit or false Trademarks, goods involving infringement of copyright, layout-design of integrated circuits, industrial designs and patents. It empowers the authorities for detention, seizures and confiscation of such counterfeited or infringing goods. This support for intellectual property enforcement as an effective border measure is provided under Sections 15, 16, 17 and 156 of the Customs Act, 1969.

4.5. The Federal Investigation Agency Act, 1974

The violation of the copyrights under the Copyright Ordinance, 1962 (amended in 2000) is included in the Schedule of the Federal Investigation Agency Act, 1974 (VIII of 1974)¹⁸. The FIA is an elite agency having good repute of taking effective measures and control against white color crimes in the country. This linkage of violation of copyright offences with FIA indicates the seriousness of the Federal Government about IP enforcement.

¹⁶ The Pakistan Penal Code, 1860 (PPC, 1860). <https://www.fmu.gov.pk/docs/laws/Pakistan%20Penal%20Code.pdf>

¹⁷ The Custom Act, 1969 (IV of 1969). <https://download1.fbr.gov.pk/Docs/20117161572837289customsAct.pdf>

¹⁸ The Federal Investigation Agency Act, 1974. <https://fia.gov.pk/act>

4.6. The Pakistan Electronic Media Regulatory Authority Act, 2002

The Federal Government taking measures for effective IPRs enforcement in media industry as well. The subject of violation of copyrights like digital contents or copyright work on the electronic media has provided protection under Section 20(g) of the Pakistan Electronic Media Regulatory Authority Act, 2002(amended 2007) (PEMRA, 2007)¹⁹. This provision restricts broadcasting or distribution of any program or advertisement in violation of copyright or other property right.

4.7. The Punjab Food Authority Act, 2011²⁰

The violation of IPRs specially Trademark and Copyrights for example false advertisement and false labeling is punishable up to one year imprisonment and or fine of rupee two Million under Sections 25 and 26 of Punjab Food Authority Act, 2011²⁰. This legal obligation strongly discourages the false production, labeling and advertisement of illicit or counterfeit products or goods.

4.8. The Plant Breeder's Act, 2016

The Plant Breeder' Act, 2016²¹ of Pakistan was promogulated in year 2016 and unlikely, the administration of this IP was handed over to the Federal Ministry of National Food Security and Research (MNFSR) of the Pakistan. This law enabled protection of new plant's varieties in the country, especially for the support of farmers and promotion of research-based agriculture industry.

4.9. The Geographical Indication Act, 2020

Pakistan's economy is highly depended on agriculture. In year 2022, agriculture contributed around 22.35 percent to the GDP of Pakistan. A notable share of export is also obtained from exporting agriculturally based products like wheat, rice, cotton and fruits. The Pakistan is rich in geographical products which are recognized due to their repute related to a specific origin. These products are known as Geographical Indication (GI). Some world-famous products of Pakistan's origin include *Basmati Rice, Pink Rock Salt, Sindhi Ajrak, Sargodha Kinnow and Chonsa Mango etc.* The Geographical Indication law remained a dire need of the country to claim value addition of Pakistan's product as GI.

However, the Geographical Indication Act, 2020 (GI Act, 2020) of Pakistan was promogulated on March 31, 2020. Before GI Act, 2020, there were provisions of protection of GI products under Certification Mark and Collective Marks in the Trade Marks Ordinance 2001. However, a *sui generis* GI law was the right solution to the public demand and for business in the international market. Accordingly, Pakistan's this legislation enabled exporters to do legal business and marketing of certified Pakistan's products in the global market. This was another supporting step to IP enforcement in the country.

5. IP Enforcement Coordination System

The public departments joined hands for the coordinated efforts required for the enforcement of Intellectual property in the country. The said partnership was formalized by signing Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) between these departments and information sharing. These departments include Federal Government and Provincial departments including IPO Pakistan, Pakistan Customs, Federal Board of Revenue (FBR), Federal Investigation Agency (FIA), Pakistan Electronic Media Regulatory Authority

¹⁹ *The Pakistan Electronic Media Regulatory Authority Act, 2002.* https://pid.gov.pk/uploads/media_laws/Ordinance_2002.pdf

²⁰ *The Punjab Food Authority Act, 2011.*: <http://punjablaws.gov.pk/laws/2460.html>

²¹ *Plant Breeder right Registry.* <https://pbrr.gov.pk/>

(PEMRA), Provincial Police departments, Drug Regulatory Authority of Pakistan (DRAP) and Food Regulatory authorities.

5.1. Establishment of Intellectual Property Tribunals

The special Intellectual Property Tribunals (IP Tribunal) were established under Section 16 of the IPO Act, 2012 by the Federal Government for speedy disposal of the suits and proceedings instituted in any court under Intellectual Property laws. The IP Tribunal were introduced instead of the Distract Courts, having the jurisdiction for the trial of case related to infringement or violation of IP Laws including Patents, Trademarks, Designs, Layout-Design of Integrated Circuits, Geographical Indications and Copyrights. The special IP qualified judges are appointed as IP tribunals and their capacity building is also being observed from time to time. IP Tribunals have exclusive jurisdiction to try any offence under Intellectual Property Laws.

Appellate authority against the final judgment or order of the IP Tribunal is the High Court having territorial jurisdiction. This makes enforcement of IP rights easier for aggrieved party. At present, there are five IP Tribunals have been established with legal jurisdiction as listed below in Table 5:

Table 5. Legal Jurisdiction of IP Tribunal in Pakistan.

IP Tribunal	Jurisdiction
Intellectual Property Tribunal, Islamabad	Federal Capital Islamabad and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province
Intellectual Property Tribunal, Rawalpindi	Rawalpindi Division, Punjab
Intellectual Property Tribunal, Lahore	Punjab Province
Intellectual Property Tribunal, Quetta	Balochistan Province
Intellectual Property Tribunal, Karachi	Sindh Province

5.2. IPR Enforcement Coordination Committees

The coordination among the concerned departments is key of success to achieve a special goal where subject is dealt by multiple departments. IPO-Pakistan entered into mutual agreements, formally referred as Memorandum of Understanding (MoU), with Pakistan Customs, Federal Board of Revenue (FBR); Security Exchange Commission of Pakistan (SECP) and other concerned departments. This minimizing the gap between the Federal Government departments resulted satisfactory outcomes.

The mandate given under section 13 and 37 of the IPO Act, 2012, the IPO-Pakistan has constituted eleven (11) special Committees on IPR enforcement²² in the major cities of Pakistan including Islamabad, Karachi, Lahore, Peshawar, Quetta, Gilgit, Multan, Sukkur, Faisalabad, Sialkot and Hyderabad. These IPR Enforcement Committees chaired by IPO Pakistan and the members are taken from the concerned Law and Enforcement Agencies and Regulatory authorities i.e. Police, Customs, PEMRA, Federal Board of Revenue (FBR), FIA, Chamber of Commerce & Industry, DRAP and Food Departments etc.

5.3. Anti-piracy and Anti-counterfeiting Cell at IPO Pakistan

In addition to constitution of eleven (11) special Committees on IPR enforcement, the organization established four (04) Anti-piracy and Anti-counterfeiting Cells²³ at multiple stations including Islamabad, Karachi, Lahore and Peshawar. The dedicated experts / professional officers have been appointed at these Cells to receive the complaints against violation of IP rights (Infringement or piracy) and to forward

²² Composition of IPR Enforcement Coordination Committee. https://ipo.gov.pk/ipr_committees

²³ Antipiracy and Anti-Counterfeiting Cells. Available at: https://ipo.gov.pk/anti_piracy_anti_counterfeiting_cell

concerned Law and Enforcement agency after preliminary investigation or confirmation and scrutiny, mandated under section 13 and 37 of the IPO Act, 2012.

5.4. Capacity Building of IP Personnel

It has been noticed that IPO Pakistan is organizing special capacity building sessions for representatives of Law and Enforcement agencies, judges, media personal and Chamber of Commerce & Industries. The LEAs includes Customs, PEMRA, Police, FIA and Regulatory Authorities. These training sessions includes local and foreign training courses and training workshops. Reportedly, around 19 such courses were offered to aforementioned personnel of LEAs²⁴.

5.5. IPR Enforcement Data 2020

As a positive outcome of aforesaid initiatives, the LEAs is performing better in respect of IPRs enforcement. The number of complaints received, complaints registered, action taken and final disposal as relief granted is increasing day by day. However, the data for year 2020 is shown below in the table 6²⁵.

Table 6. Actions taken by Law Enforcement agencies against IPR Violations.

SN	Enforcement Agency	Nature of IP offence	IPR Cases registered Actions taken
1	Federal Investigation Agency	Copyright Violation	61
2	Pakistan Customs	Border Measure	21
3	Pakistan Electronic Media Regulatory Authority (PEMRA)	Signal Piracy	04 (03 TV channels were fined Rs. 100,000)
	TOTAL		86

6. Impact of Record Digitization & Business Process Automation

The organization made digitization its historical record of 50 years during 2006 and from onward application are received and captured by the System. This digitization of historical record includes patents, designs, trademarks and copyrights. In addition to digitization, the IP business processes of IP application, from reception to registration and post registration, were also automated by this system. The availability of a centralized IP application record database, made it easy to process IP application and to share information for IPR enforcement purposes too. IPO Pakistan has launched a rich informative website where almost all the standard required information like IP legislation, fee, forms, applications filing guidelines, FAQs, e-journal, publications, application filing and grant data, officer contact directory, IP Help desk, Anti-piracy and Anti-counterfeiting Cell, List of Technology Innovation support Centers (TISC), list of Patent and Trademark agents etc. are available. The Organization has started electronic filing of IP Application along with e-payments which is further facilitating the applicants to get speedy their registration by saving their resources, in terms of cost and time, at their home.

²⁴ Training Sessions/Capacity Building of IPR Enforcement Agencies. Available at: <https://ipo.gov.pk/node/128>

²⁵ IPR Enforcement Data 2020. Available at: <https://ipo.gov.pk/node/128>

7. IP Application Filing and Registration Trends

The collective statistics of application filing of trademarks, patents, designs and copyrights has been increased after inception of IPO Pakistan. This trend reflects the trust of local businessmen and international investors and attracts for investment in Pakistan. Figure 1 shows the IP applications received by IPO offices during 2020 to 2023 (IP Application Statistics)²⁶.

Figure 1. IP application filing trends in Pakistan.

8. Conclusions

The overall impact of integrated IP management after the establishment of central organization, IPO Pakistan, is encouraging in the country. The IPRs enforcement indicators are developing positive progress. The filing and registrations of IP applications have been increased during the last few years. The share of IP applications filed by the resident increased due to trust on the IP system and its enforcement. Pakistan has entered in to new era of IP compliant country by signing international treaties on IP including Madrid protocol for trademarks and Marrakash Treaty on copyrights for VIPs in the recent past. Further, Pakistan is preparing to join Patent Cooperation Treaty (PCT)²⁷ and Hague System for Industrial Designs. Resultantly, situation of IPRs enforcement is better and international IP ranking of the country is improving with passage of time. This indication of progress in the IPRs state ranking will be supportive for wining trust of foreign investment and shall be fostering the national economy.

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²⁷ IPO Pakistan official Website. IP Legislation. IP Legislation in process. Drafts of Proposed Amendments in the Patents Ordinance, 2000 and Pakistan's Accession to Patent Cooperation Treaty (PCT). https://ipo.gov.pk/ip_legislation_in_process

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